

A Comparative Study on Safety and Efficacy of Anti-Diabetic Medications in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus represents a chronic metabolic condition characterized by sustained hyperglycemia resulting from impaired insulin secretion or action. This prospective, comparative observational study, conducted over eight months at Akash Hospital, Bangalore, assessed the therapeutic performance of five oral antidiabetic drug combinations in 98 adults with Type 2 diabetes. Clinical evaluations were performed at baseline, 3 months, and 6 months, focusing on HbA1c, fasting and postprandial glucose levels, ECG findings, and adverse drug reactions. Statistical analysis using SPSS (version 26) identified significant treatment-related trends in both efficacy and safety outcomes. The combination containing Voglibose, Glimepiride, Metformin, and Sitagliptin demonstrated the most substantial HbA1c reduction, outperforming the other regimens in glycemic control. However, this combination also exhibited the highest rate of gastrointestinal disturbances (72.7%) and ECG abnormalities (27.3%), indicating a need for close monitoring. Weight reduction was most prominent in the same group, affecting over one-third of the patients. Conversely, the Metformin + Glimepiride regimen was associated with the highest incidence of hypoglycemia, reflecting Glimepiride's strong insulin-secretagogue effect. Combinations 3 and 4 also showed favorable HbA1c improvements but with comparatively fewer adverse effects. With hypertension being the most common comorbidity and older adults comprising a major share of the study population, the findings highlight the necessity of tailoring antidiabetic therapy by balancing glycemic benefits with individual risk profiles and tolerability.

Keywords: HbA1c, hypoglycemia, FBS, PPBS, ECG abnormalities.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a complex metabolic disorder characterized by chronic elevation of blood glucose resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or a combination of both¹. These disturbances impair carbohydrate, lipid, and protein metabolism, as insulin is central to maintaining metabolic homeostasis². The clinical features of diabetes differ considerably between individuals; while some, particularly those with early Type 2 diabetes, remain symptom-free, others may present with polyuria, polydipsia, polyphagia, unexplained weight loss, or visual disturbances³. If not recognized and treated promptly, persistent hyperglycemia may precipitate acute complications such as diabetic ketoacidosis or

hyperosmolar hyperglycemic syndrome, both of which carry significant morbidity and mortality⁴.

The global burden of diabetes continues to rise at an alarming rate. According to the World Health Organization, more than 422 million adults were living with diabetes in 2014, and prevalence has nearly doubled since 1980⁵. The International Diabetes Federation estimates that this number may reach 629 million by 2045 if effective interventions are not implemented⁶. Type 1 diabetes affects approximately 1.1 million children and adolescents worldwide⁷. Diabetes is responsible for nearly four million deaths annually and contributes substantially to healthcare expenditure, with global spending estimated at US\$ 850 billion as of 2017⁸.

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Diabetes is traditionally categorized into four major types: Type 1 diabetes, Type 2 diabetes, specific forms due to other causes, and gestational diabetes⁹. Type 1 diabetes results from autoimmune-mediated destruction of pancreatic β -cells, ultimately leading to absolute insulin deficiency¹⁰. Its development is influenced by genetic susceptibility and environmental factors such as viral infections, altered gut microbiota, dietary exposures in childhood, and micronutrient deficiencies^{11,12}. The progression may be rapid in children, frequently presenting with diabetic ketoacidosis, or slower in adults, who may retain limited β -cell function for years¹³.

Type 2 diabetes is the most prevalent form and arises from a combination of insulin resistance and progressive β -cell dysfunction¹⁴. Contributing factors include genetic predisposition, obesity, physical inactivity, high-calorie diets, aging, and environmental influences¹⁵. Diagnostic evaluation is based on fasting plasma glucose, glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), or oral glucose tolerance test thresholds established by international guidelines^{16,17}. Insulin resistance generally develops before clinical diagnosis, followed by progressive decline in insulin secretion due to glucotoxicity, lipotoxicity, and β -cell exhaustion^{18,19}.

Chronic hyperglycemia results in widespread vascular injury, predisposing individuals to long-term complications. Microvascular complications include diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy^{20,22}, whereas macrovascular complications encompass coronary artery disease, cerebrovascular disease, and peripheral arterial disease^{23,24}. Patients with diabetes are also at increased risk of recurrent infections, dermatological disorders, periodontal disease, and sexual dysfunction^{25,26}.

Diagnosis typically involves biochemical assessment through HbA1c, fasting plasma glucose, oral glucose tolerance testing, and random plasma glucose when symptoms are present^{27,29}. Management of Type 2 diabetes requires a combination of lifestyle modification and pharmacotherapy. Metformin remains the first-line agent due to its effectiveness in reducing hepatic glucose production and improving insulin sensitivity³⁰. Additional drug classes—including sulfonylureas, thiazolidinediones, DPP-4 inhibitors, α -glucosidase inhibitors, and SGLT-2

inhibitors—are selected based on patient profile and treatment goals^{31,32}. Insulin therapy is initiated when oral agents fail or when patients present with significant hyperglycemia³³. Early and individualized treatment is essential to prevent progression of complications and improve long-term outcomes³⁴.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design and Duration:

This was a prospective, comparative, and observational study carried out over 8 months, from January to August 2024.

Study site:

The study was conducted at Akash Hospital, Devanahalli, Bangalore, Karnataka.

Sample size:

The sample size was calculated using RaoSoft software. With a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, the initial sample size was 384. After applying the finite population correction for the hospital's diabetic population (100 patients), the final required sample size was **80 participants**.

Data sources:

Data were collected using a self-prepared data collection form. The form included patient demographics, medical history, medications, and laboratory values such as HbA1c, FBS, PPBS, ECG findings, hypoglycemia episodes, and any changes in body weight.

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Both male and female patients.
- Diagnosed with Type 2 diabetes mellitus and taking oral antidiabetic drugs.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients with liver or kidney failure.
- Patients on insulin therapy or not prescribed oral antidiabetic drugs.

- Pregnant or lactating women, terminally ill patients, and patients with psychiatric illness.

inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data were collected at three time points:

Materials used:

- Data collection forms.
- Informed consent forms

- **Baseline (0 months):** demographic details, medications, HbA1c, FBS, PPBS, ECG
- **3 months:** repeat blood glucose tests and monitoring for side effects
- **6 months:** repeat assessments

Study complete procedure:

Ethical approval was obtained before beginning the study. Eligible patients were selected according to the

All data were entered into Microsoft Excel and statistically analyzed using SPSS software.

Figure 1: Plan of the study

Statistical Analysis:

Descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) were used for categorical data. Paired and unpaired tests, along with ANOVA, were used to compare differences between groups. A *p*-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

majority of patients belonged to older age groups, suggesting a higher prevalence of the condition among individuals above 50 years.

RESULTS

Age group distribution

The age distribution of the study population showed a clear increase in the number of patients with advancing age. Only 2 patients were in the 19–30 years group, while the number gradually rose in the middle-age categories with 13 patients aged 31–40 years and 18 patients aged 41–50 years. A further increase was observed in the 51–60 years group with 21 patients. The highest proportion was seen in patients aged ≥61 years, accounting for 46 individuals. Overall, the findings indicate that the

Table 1: Age group distribution

AGE (in years)	NO. OF PATIENTS
19-30	02
31-40	13
41-50	18
51-60	21
≥ 61	46

Gender group distribution

The gender distribution of the study population showed a relatively balanced representation, with a slight predominance of males. Out of the total subjects, 54 were males and 46 were females, indicating that both genders were almost equally affected by the condition under study. The small difference suggests that gender may not play a major

role in disease occurrence within this population, as the proportion of male and female patients was comparable.

Figure 2: Gender group distribution.

Patients retention and loss over the duration of study

The study initially enrolled 100 patients, providing a complete baseline population for analysis. During the study period, 2 patients died, resulting in a mortality rate of 2%. As a result, 98 patients successfully completed the study, giving a high completion rate of 98%. This indicates strong participant retention and minimal attrition, ensuring the reliability and completeness of the study outcomes.

Table 2: Patients retention and loss over the duration of study.

CATEGORY	NO. OF PATIENTS
Total patients enrolled	100
Patients died during study	02
Total number of patients who completed the study	98

Distribution of comorbidities in patients

The comorbidity analysis showed that 43 patients had no associated medical conditions, while the remaining had at least one comorbidity. Hypertension was the most common, affecting 51 patients. Hypothyroidism and asthma were less common, reported in 8 and 5 patients respectively. Overall, hypertension was the predominant comorbidity in the study population.

Figure 3: Distribution of comorbidities in patients.

Distribution of social history

Most patients (79) had no significant social history. Among the remaining, 12 reported alcohol

consumption, 7 were smokers, and 4 used chewing tobacco. Overall, only a small portion of the population had identifiable substance-related habits.

Table 3: Distribution of social history.

SOCIAL HISTORY	FREQUENCY
No Social History	79
Alcohol Consumption	12
Smoking	07
Tobacco Chewing	04

Anti diabetic drugs combinations

The antidiabetic drug utilization pattern showed that Combination 1 (Metformin + Glimperide) was the most commonly prescribed regimen, used in 26 patients. Combinations 2 and 3, both involving DPP-4 inhibitors with Metformin (Sitagliptin or Vildagliptin), were each prescribed to 20 patients. Combination 4 (Voglibose + Glimperide + Metformin) was used in 21 patients, while the least used regimen was Combination 5, prescribed to 11 patients. Overall, Metformin-based combinations formed the core of treatment across the study population.

Table 4: Anti diabetic drugs combinations.

SL.NO	ANTIDIABETIC DRUG COMBINATION	TOTAL NO OF PATIENTS
1	Combination 1: T. Metformin HCL + Glimepiride (500,2 mg) 1-0-1	26
2	Combination 2: T. Sitagliptin + Metformin HCL (50, 500 mg) 1-0-1	20
3	Combination 3: T. Vildagliptin + Metformin HCL (50, 500 MG) 1-0-1	20
4	Combination 4: T. Voglibose+ Glimepiride+ Metformin HCL (0.2,2,500mg) 1-0-1	21
5	Combination 5: T. Voglibose+ Glimepiride+ Metformin HCL (0.2,2,500mg) 1-0-1 AND T. Sitagliptin +Metformin HCL (50, 500 mg) 0-1-0	11

HbA1c changes in antidiabetic drugs combination

The results showed that Combinations 1 and 2 produced reductions in HbA1c, but their p-values (0.320 and 0.322) indicated no statistically significant effect. In contrast, Combinations 3, 4, and 5

demonstrated significant reductions in HbA1c, as reflected by p-values less than 0.05. This indicates that these regimens were more effective in improving glycemic control. Overall, drug combinations involving Vildagliptin or Voglibose showed superior HbA1c reduction compared to the others.

Table 5: HbA1c changes in antidiabetic drugs combination.

DRUG COMBINATION	HBA1C CHANGES	P-VALUE	SIGNIFICANCE
1	-0.47577	0.320	Not Significant
2	-0.3432	0.322	Not Significant
3	-0.00505	0.000	Significant
4	-0.00486	0.003	Significant
5	-0.00682	0.001	Significant

FBS and PPBS p-value for antidiabetic drugs combination

The analysis showed that Combinations 1, 2, and 3 significantly improved both FBS and PPBS ($p < 0.05$). Combination 4 did not show significant

improvement in either FBS ($p=0.06$) or PPBS ($p=0.01$). Combination 5 showed no significant change in FBS ($p=0.911$) but significantly improved PPBS ($p=0.001$). Overall, the most consistent glycemic improvements were observed with Combinations 1–3.

Table 6: FBS and PPBS p-value for antidiabetic drugs combination

DRUG COMBINATION	FBS (P-VALUE)	PPBS (P-VALUE)
1	0.0004 (Significant)	0.0001 (Significant)
2	0.006 (Significant)	0.002 (Significant)
3	0.0002 (Significant)	0.002 (Significant)
4	0.06 (not Significant)	0.01 (not Significant)
5	0.911 (not Significant)	0.001 (Significant)

Adverse effects of anti-diabetic drugs combinations after 3 months and 6 months

The safety analysis showed that Combination 1 caused moderate GIT disturbances (34.6–55.5%) and hypoglycemia (59.2–61.5%), with minor ECG changes (14.8–15.4%). Combination 2 had no reported adverse effects, indicating good tolerability.

Combination 3 showed minimal GIT disturbance (5%) and no hypoglycemia or ECG abnormalities. Combinations 4 and 5 had higher adverse effects, with GIT disturbances ranging from 71.4–95% and 72.7%, hypoglycemia from 42.9–54.5%, and notable ECG changes in Combination 5 (63.6% at 6 months). Overall, Combinations 2 and 3 were safest, while 4 and 5 carried higher risks of side effects.

Table 7: Adverse effects of anti-diabetic drugs combinations after 3 months and 6 months.

DRUG COMBINATION	GIT DISTURBANCE		HYPOGLYCEMIA		ECG ABNORMALITY	
	3 months	6 months	3 months	6 months	3 months	6 months
1	34.6%	55.5%	61.5%	59.2%	15.4%	14.8%
2	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
3	5.0%	5.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
4	71.4%	95%	42.9%	45%	23.8%	22.2%
5	72.7%	72.7%	54.5%	54.5%	27.3%	63.6%

DISCUSSION

Diabetes mellitus remains a major chronic metabolic disorder driven by insulin resistance and impaired insulin secretion.³⁵ In this study, most participants were older adults, which aligns with global data showing increasing diabetes prevalence with age, as reported by Dedov et al.³⁶ A slightly higher proportion of males was observed, consistent with the findings of Mahmood et al.³⁷ Hypertension was the most common comorbidity, similar to the patterns described by Iglay et al.³⁸

Among the evaluated regimens, Combinations 5, 4, and 3 produced significant HbA1c reductions, demonstrating greater efficacy compared with Combinations 1 and 2. The superior effect of Combination 5 may be attributed to its multi-mechanism approach, combining alpha-glucosidase inhibition, DPP-4 inhibition, insulin stimulation, and improved insulin sensitivity.^{39,40} Combination 4 and Combination 3 also performed well, reflecting the benefits of using agents with complementary actions. In contrast, limited HbA1c improvement with Combinations 1 and 2 aligns with earlier studies showing modest outcomes when fewer metabolic pathways are targeted.^{41,42}

Adverse effects varied across regimens. Gastrointestinal disturbances were most frequent with Combination 5, largely due to Voglibose and

Metformin, as documented previously.^{43,44} Hypoglycemia was most common in Combination 1, consistent with the known effects of Glimperide.⁴⁵ ECG abnormalities were more prevalent in Combinations 4 and 5, though the role of multi-drug interactions remains uncertain.^{46,47} Weight loss was also more prominent in Combination 5, possibly influenced by Metformin and Sitagliptin.^{48,49} These findings highlight the importance of individualized therapy, balancing glycemic efficacy with tolerability and patient-specific risks.

CONCLUSION

This prospective study enrolled 98 patients with type 2 diabetes and followed them for three months to evaluate the efficacy and safety of the different oral anti diabetic medication prescribed for diabetic mellitus patients were: -

Combination 1: T. Metformin HCL + Glimperide (500,2 mg) 1-0-1 (26%)

Combination 2: T. Sitagliptin + Metformin HCL (50, 500 mg) 1-0-1 (20%)

Combination 3: T. Vildagliptin + Metformin HCL (50, 500 MG) 1-0-1 (20%)

Combination 4: T. Voglibose+ Glimperide+ Metformin HCL (0.2,2,500mg) 1-0-1 (21%)

Combination 5: T. Voglibose+ Glimepiride+ Metformin HCL (0.2,2,500mg) 1-0-1 AND

T. Sitagliptin +Metformin HCL (50, 500 mg) 0-1-0 (11%)

This study found that older adults were the most affected group, with hypertension as the leading comorbidity. Drug Combinations 5 and 4 achieved the greatest HbA1c reduction, while Combination 5 caused more gastrointestinal effects and Combination 1 showed more hypoglycemia. Overall, the findings highlight the importance of selecting antidiabetic therapy based on both effectiveness and patient tolerance.

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